

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17426840

Exploring the Role of Emotional Intelligence in Enhancing Lecturers' Job Productivity in Universities in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated how emotional intelligence affects job productivity among university lecturers in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. The study employed an ex-post facto design using a descriptive survey approach, which allowed data collection without manipulating any study variables. The target population comprised 4,426 lecturers working in both federal and state universities across the two states. A stratified random sampling method was applied to select 1,394 participants, ensuring fair representation across institutional type, academic rank, and discipline. Data were gathered using two standardized instruments: Emotional Intelligence Assessment Questionnaire (EIAQ) and Lecturers' Job Productivity Assessment Questionnaire (LJPAQ). Expert validation confirmed the content validity of both instruments, while reliability was established with Cronbach's Alpha values of 0.88 for the EIAQ and 0.85 for the LJPAQ. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23, where descriptive statistics such as mean and coefficient of determination addressed the research questions, and independent sample t-tests were used for hypothesis testing. The results indicated that emotional intelligence had a significant positive impact on job productivity. Lecturers in Edo State demonstrated marginally higher levels of emotional intelligence and productivity than their counterparts in Delta State. Consequently, the study recommends that universities promote emotional intelligence training programs and incorporate emotional intelligence competencies into professional development and promotion frameworks.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Job Productivity, Lecturers, Professional Development

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, emotional intelligence (EI) has gained considerable attention for its vital role in both professional and academic contexts. EI refers to an individual's capacity to recognize, comprehend, regulate, and utilize emotions—both their own and those of others—to foster positive interactions, improve communication, and enhance overall performance across different environments (Babatunde et al., 2023). Within the context of higher education, lecturers are constantly engaged in complex interactions with students, colleagues, and administration, where EI can significantly influence their

ability to perform their duties effectively. In Nigerian universities, where lecturers face challenges such as large class sizes, administrative pressure, and diverse student needs, emotional intelligence has the potential to serve as a crucial factor in boosting both individual and institutional outcomes.

As emotional intelligence continues to gain prominence as a fundamental factor in professional effectiveness, its core dimensions, self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy (social awareness), and social skills (relationship management), have become focal points of interest in educational and organizational research. These components collectively influence how effectively lecturers perform their roles in the classroom. Through self-awareness, lecturers can identify and understand their emotional states and how these affect their teaching style and interactions with students. Self-regulation, on the other hand, equips them to control their emotions, maintain composure, and respond appropriately even in stressful or challenging teaching situations. Motivation, on the other hand, drives lecturers to maintain high levels of energy and persistence, even when faced with the demands of teaching and research. Empathy, or social awareness, allows lecturers to understand and relate to their students' emotional needs, facilitating better student engagement and communication. Finally, social skills help lecturers build rapport, collaborate with colleagues, and resolve conflicts, which are essential for effective teaching and a positive academic environment (Nicole et al., 2025; Shi & Cheung, 2024).

Given the significant role that emotional intelligence plays in academic settings, it is crucial to understand how EI affects lecturers' job productivity. Job productivity encompasses a wide range of tasks, including preparing lecture materials, delivering lessons, supervising student projects, grading assignments, and engaging in research. Research suggests that emotional intelligence positively impacts job performance by enhancing lecturers' ability to manage stress, foster positive relationships, and navigate complex social dynamics (Akpan et al., 2025; Gidado et al., 2025). In Nigerian universities, where lecturers are often faced with heavy workloads and diverse student populations, EI may serve as a valuable resource in ensuring productivity and professional success.

While the connection between emotional intelligence and job productivity has been well-documented in other contexts, there remains a notable gap in research specifically examining this relationship among university lecturers in Nigeria, particularly in Delta and Edo States (DES). Studies such as those by Ogbeta-Ogwu (2024) and Ajake et al. (2025) have examined the general role of emotional intelligence in Nigerian educators' performance, but few have focused on regional variations or how EI may influence productivity in different geographical settings. This gap is significant because the educational climate, resources, and institutional support can vary substantially across states, which might impact the relationship between EI and job productivity (Hamid, 2025). Therefore, there is a clear need to examine how emotional intelligence influences lecturers' job performance in these specific regions of Nigeria.

Moreover, while emotional intelligence has been shown to enhance job productivity, the relationship is not always consistent across various academic institutions or regions. Institutional culture, regional policies, and access to professional development opportunities can all influence how EI impacts productivity (Zhi et al., 2024). For instance, universities in Edo State may have more established support systems for EI training, which could lead to stronger effects on lecturers' productivity compared to those in Delta State. This study, therefore, sought to assess the emotional intelligence levels of lecturers in Delta and Edo States and examine how emotional intelligence impacts their job productivity within Nigerian university contexts. Through this investigation, the research aims to provide meaningful insights into the contribution of emotional intelligence to lecturers' professional effectiveness and propose strategies that universities can adopt to harness EI for improved teaching performance and overall institutional outcomes.

The justification for this study arises from the existing gap in literature concerning how emotional intelligence affects job productivity among university lecturers in DES, Nigeria. While much has been written on the broader application of EI in education, specific studies focusing on Nigerian universities and their regional disparities are scarce. This research sought to address that gap by examining the impact of emotional intelligence on the job productivity of university lecturers in Delta and Edo States. The findings could provide critical recommendations for educational policy and professional development

programmes, guiding universities in enhancing the emotional and professional capacities of their lecturers. In doing so, the study will provide deeper insights into how emotional intelligence can serve as a strategic tool for enhancing job performance and, consequently, improving the overall quality of education in Nigerian universities.

Statement of the Problem

The significance of emotional intelligence in improving lecturers' job productivity has attracted growing interest in educational research, especially in advanced nations. Nevertheless, there remains a scarcity of empirical evidence examining the effect of emotional intelligence on lecturers' productivity within Nigerian universities, particularly in DES. Considering the multifaceted nature of academic work—which encompasses teaching, research, mentorship, and administrative responsibilities—lecturers must effectively manage their own emotions while responding to the varying emotional demands of their students. In this context, understanding the emotional intelligence of lecturers in these regions could offer valuable insights into their ability to perform effectively in their multifaceted roles. Moreover, emotional intelligence has the potential to enhance lecturers' resilience, stress management, and interpersonal skills, which are essential for productivity in the challenging academic environments of Nigerian universities. Thus, examining this relationship could inform the design of interventions aimed at improving lecturers' performance, well-being, and overall contribution to institutional success.

Although existing research has increasingly established a link between emotional intelligence and job productivity, there is still a notable lack of studies focusing on university lecturers in Nigeria, especially within DES. These states provide unique educational and socio-cultural environments that may shape how emotional intelligence relates to lecturers' performance. Variations in regional policies, institutional resources, and access to professional development could lead to differing emotional intelligence levels among lecturers, which in turn may affect their productivity. Considering these contextual factors and the relevance of emotional intelligence and productivity in academia, this study seeks to address a key question: What is the influence of emotional intelligence on the job productivity of lecturers in universities located in DES, Nigeria?

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and job productivity among university lecturers in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the level of emotional intelligence exhibited by lecturers in universities within DES;
2. Assess the level of job productivity among lecturers in universities within the same region; and
3. Analyze how emotional intelligence influences the job productivity of university lecturers in DES.

Research Questions

The research was structured on three questions:

1. What is the level of emotional intelligence of lecturers in Universities in DES?
2. What is the level of lecturers' job productivity in Universities in DES?
3. What is the influence of emotional intelligence on lecturers' job productivity in Universities in DES?

Hypothesis

One hypothesis further guided this study:

1. There is no significant difference between DES regarding the influence of emotional intelligence on lecturers' job productivity.

METHODS

This study utilized an ex-post facto research design supported by a descriptive survey approach. This design was considered appropriate since it focused on gathering data about existing conditions without manipulating any variables, thereby facilitating an objective assessment of the relationship between emotional intelligence and job productivity among university lecturers. The descriptive survey method allowed the researcher to collect information from a broad and diverse population in their natural work

environment, making it ideal for examining how emotional intelligence influences lecturers' productivity across DES.

The study population consisted of 4,426 lecturers working in public universities in DES. This group included lecturers from both federal and state-owned universities, covering a variety of academic fields such as education, sciences, engineering, humanities, management, and law. The population encompassed lecturers across all academic ranks—from Assistant Lecturer to Professor—reflecting varying levels of academic and administrative duties. To ensure proper representation, a stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select 1,394 lecturers. The stratification was based on key factors such as academic discipline, institutional ownership, and rank. Random selection within each stratum minimized bias and enhanced the generalizability of the findings to the larger population of lecturers in the two states.

Data were gathered using two researcher-developed instruments. The first, the Emotional Intelligence Assessment Questionnaire (EIAQ), measured the extent to which lecturers demonstrate emotional intelligence in their professional roles. It assessed domains such as self-awareness, empathy, motivation, self-regulation, and social skills. The second instrument, the Lecturers' Job Productivity Assessment Questionnaire (LJPAQ), captured self-reported indicators of job productivity, including teaching quality, research engagement, student supervision, participation in academic governance, and community service. Both tools used a four-point Likert scale: the EIAQ ranged from "Very Low" to "Very High," while the LJPAQ ranged from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree."

To establish validity, the instruments were reviewed by three experts in educational psychology and measurement and evaluation, whose feedback guided revisions for improved clarity and alignment with the study objectives. For reliability, a pilot test was conducted with 40 lecturers from a university outside the study area. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients obtained were 0.88 for the EIAQ and 0.85 for the LJPAQ, demonstrating high internal consistency.

Hard copies of the questionnaires were personally administered and retrieved by the researcher across the selected universities to ensure a high response rate and data accuracy. Ethical standards were maintained throughout the research process. Participants were fully informed of the study's purpose, assured of confidentiality and anonymity, and gave their informed consent voluntarily before participating.

Data collected were analyzed using the SPSS version 23. Descriptive statistics such as mean and coefficient of determination were used to address the research questions, providing insight into the degree of emotional intelligence and its perceived impact on job productivity. To test the hypotheses, independent sample t-tests were conducted to determine whether significant differences existed between lecturers in DES regarding the effect of emotional intelligence on job productivity. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Level of Emotional Intelligence of Lecturers in Universities in DES

S/N	Item	Delta			Edo		
		M	SD	R	M	SD	R
Self-Awareness							
1	I understand my mood in any situation	3.02	0.94	H	3.47	0.88	H
2	I can easily decipher my emotions	3.55	0.92	H	3.55	0.79	H
3	I am capable of coping with other people	2.83	0.61	H	3.25	0.62	H
4	I am open to new things	3.38	0.61	H	3.45	0.61	H
5	I can cope with difficult people	2.69	0.97	H	3.38	0.77	H
6	I easily release my anger	2.98	0.84	H	3.18	0.74	H
7	I know when other people are angry with me	3.13	0.88	H	3.32	0.84	H
8	My self-awareness capability has improved my academic productivity	3.30	0.94	H	3.42	0.87	H
Cluster Mean Social		3.06	0.89	H	3.26	0.80	H

Awareness/Empathy							
9	I listen attentively when others speak	3.13	0.77	H	3.18	0.76	H
10	I put myself in others' situation	3.45	0.56	H	3.52	0.61	H
11	I share the pains of others	3.15	0.83	H	3.25	0.63	H
12	I help others when they are in difficult situations	3.40	0.76	H	3.55	0.68	H
13	I can decipher if someone is unhappy with me	3.35	0.79	H	3.50	0.74	H
14	I understand when I am unreasonable	3.55	0.72	VH	3.15	0.67	H
15	I can understand the behavior of other people	2.77	0.75	H	3.15	0.65	H
16	I can get along with people even when they offend me	2.81	0.80	H	3.20	0.63	H
Cluster Mean		3.13	0.72	H	3.34	0.74	H
Self-Management							
17	I can stay focused when I am pressured	2.85	0.98	H	3.35	0.92	H
18	In trying moments, I stay focused	3.40	0.97	H	3.55	0.68	VH
19	I do not easily get angry with difficult people	2.80	0.79	H	3.45	0.76	H
20	I can easily reframe bad situations	3.25	0.88	H	3.20	0.91	H
21	I easily bounce back after a setback	3.00	1.01	H	3.30	1.05	H
22	I can adapt my responses to fit my circumstances	3.30	0.94	H	3.45	0.69	H
23	I can self-control	2.75	0.64	H	3.50	0.56	VH
24	I can say that my self-management skill improved my productivity	2.90	0.59	H	3.25	0.66	H
Cluster Mean		3.03	0.85	H	3.40	0.85	H
Self-Motivation							
25	I see new opportunities when I am angry	2.51	1.11	H	3.40	0.61	H
26	In the face of difficulties, I use a good mood to adapt	3.40	0.61	H	3.10	0.78	H
27	I engage in activities that bring me satisfaction	2.63	1.09	H	3.55	0.95	VH
28	I always work hard to meet deadlines	3.30	1.10	H	3.20	0.84	H
29	I can come up with innovative ideas when I experience change in my emotions	3.25	0.52	H	3.35	1.03	H
30	I am always willing to handle difficult situations	3.60	0.50	VH	3.50	0.47	VH
31	I can say that because of my self-motivation, I have improved greatly in the performance of my responsibilities	3.00	0.94	H	3.40	0.63	H
Cluster Mean		3.10	0.84	H	3.35	0.79	H
Relationship Management							
32	I enjoy being around people	3.30	0.63	H	3.20	0.94	H
33	I can manage conflict among peers	2.90	0.56	H	3.30	0.56	H
34	I can easily build relationships in my school	3.15	0.71	H	3.45	0.70	H
35	I am good at mixing up with people	3.00	0.83	H	3.35	0.69	H
36	I can negotiate when there is conflict	2.70	1.00	H	3.25	0.70	H
37	I am a good listener to others	2.60	0.98	H	3.50	0.82	VH
38	I always ask questions on issues before concluding	3.60	0.97	VH	3.60	0.68	VH
39	I consider decision-making by consensus opinion	2.61	0.79	H	3.40	0.87	H
40	I can say that my ability to manage relationships enhanced my productivity	3.50	0.88	VH	3.10	0.91	H
Cluster Mean		3.04	0.82	H	3.35	0.76	H

Criterion Mean = 2.50, N = 1, 394 (Delta = 510, Edo = 884)

Table 1 presents data on the emotional intelligence levels of lecturers in DES. The findings indicate that lecturers in Delta State exhibit a high level of emotional intelligence, as evidenced by the cluster mean scores across all measured components. The overall grand mean for Delta State is 3.04, with a standard deviation of 0.82, and the rating is H (High). Similarly, the data from Edo State universities show that lecturers also possess a high level of emotional intelligence, supported by the overall cluster means. The grand mean for Edo State is slightly higher at 3.37, with a standard deviation of 0.80, and the rating is H (High). Based on the results from both states, it can be inferred that lecturers in both DES have generally high levels of emotional intelligence. However, lecturers in Edo State exhibited slightly higher emotional intelligence compared to those in Delta State across all components.

Table 2: Level of Lecturers’ job Productivity in Universities in DES

S/N	Items	Delta			Edo		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Lecturers prepare their lecture notes	2.75	0.64	H	3.50	0.84	VH
2	Lecturers give students meaningful notes	3.40	0.74	H	3.15	0.61	H
3	Lecturers are punctual to class/lecture halls to teach students	2.85	0.59	H	3.00	0.61	H
4	Lecturers take attendance of students during lectures	2.95	0.80	H	3.25	0.59	H
5	Lecturers prepare students results on time	3.65	0.57	VH	3.40	0.62	H
6	Lecturers give attention to students with special needs	2.80	0.57	H	2.85	0.72	H
7	Lecturers mark students’ scripts on time	3.25	0.57	H	3.10	0.57	H
8	Lecturers accept other responsibilities	2.70	0.90	H	3.41	0.79	H
9	Lecturers assist students in solving their problems	3.45	0.57	H	3.35	0.58	H
10	Lecturers publish researches in local journals	3.70	0.65	VH	3.55	0.58	VH
11	Lecturers publish researches in international referred journal	2.65	0.64	H	3.25	0.58	H
12	Lecturers are promoted as at when due as a result of their publications	3.40	0.65	H	3.45	0.88	H
13	Lecturers supervise students research projects	2.50	0.78	H	3.60	0.58	VH
14	Lecturers provide mentorship to students they supervise	3.15	0.62	H	3.75	0.63	VH
15	Lecturers contribute chapters in a book	3.40	0.76	H	3.15	0.64	H
16	Lecturers collaborate with colleagues to publish paper in Scopus indexed journals	3.45	0.83	H	3.40	0.63	H
17	Lecturers seeks research grant to conduct cutting-edge research	2.75	0.57	H	3.50	0.77	VH
	Grand Mean	3.11	0.67	H	3.33	0.66	H

Table 2 presents the findings on the extent of lecturers’ job productivity in universities across DES. The data revealed grand mean scores of 3.11 for Delta State and 3.33 for Edo State, both exceeding the benchmark value of 2.50. This suggests that the majority of respondents perceived lecturers in both states as exhibiting a high level of job productivity. All items evaluated recorded mean scores above the cutoff, signifying consensus among respondents on the high productivity levels. Specifically, in Delta State, lecturers were rated very high in the timely preparation of student results (3.65) and publishing in local journals (3.70). In Edo State, job productivity was also perceived to be very high in the preparation of lecture materials (3.50), publishing research locally (3.55), supervising student research projects (3.60), offering mentorship to supervisees (3.75), and pursuing research grants for innovative studies (3.50). Therefore, it can be inferred that lecturers in both Delta and Edo State universities demonstrate high productivity, particularly in the areas of lecture note preparation, timely result compilation, publication in local academic journals, project supervision, mentoring students, and actively seeking research funding.

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination Showing the Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Lecturers’ Job Productivity in DES

University	Variable	N	R	R ²	R ² %	Decision
Delta	Emotional intelligence	261	0.783	0.613	61.3	Strong positive relationship
	Job productivity	249				
Edo	Emotional intelligence	460	0.843	0.711	71.1	Strong positive relationship
	Job productivity	424				

Table 3 displays the correlation analysis between emotional intelligence and lecturers’ job productivity in DES. In Delta State, the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.783$) indicates a strong positive relationship between emotional intelligence and job productivity, with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.613. This suggests that emotional intelligence contributes about 61.3% to the variation in lecturers’ productivity. In Edo State, the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.843$) also shows a strong positive link, with an R^2 value of 0.711, meaning emotional intelligence accounts for approximately 71.1% of the variance in job productivity. These findings highlight that emotional intelligence significantly and positively influences lecturers’ job performance in both states, emphasizing its importance in improving academic effectiveness and professional outcomes.

Table 4: Independent t-test Comparing DES on the Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Lecturers’ Job Productivity

State	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t_{cal}	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Delta	510	2.9960	0.36267	1,392	2.056	0.047	Significant
Edo	884	3.2155	0.31054				

Table 4 shows a significant difference between lecturers in DES in terms of how emotional intelligence affects their job productivity, as evidenced by the result ($t = 2.056$, $p = 0.047$), which is below the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that the effect of emotional intelligence on job productivity differs notably between the two states. The result favors lecturers in Edo State, suggesting that emotional intelligence exerts a stronger positive influence on their productivity compared to those in Delta State. Therefore, it can be concluded that emotional intelligence contributes differently to enhancing lecturers’ performance across the two states, with Edo State lecturers experiencing a greater benefit.

DISCUSSION

One of the findings indicated that lecturers in both states exhibit high productivity levels, particularly in key responsibilities such as lecture preparation, timely result compilation, publication in local academic journals, student supervision, mentoring activities, and pursuit of funding for advanced research. During field interactions, the researcher found numerous examples of lecturers who extended their working hours and took personal interest in their students’ academic success. This qualitative insight strongly supports the quantitative data showing high performance among the teaching staff, especially in the timely discharge of academic responsibilities and provision of mentorship. The findings correlate with those of Abiola and Ajibade (2025), who documented a similar pattern of strong work ethic and high engagement among university lecturers despite structural challenges such as underfunding and large class sizes. Consistent with these observations, this study confirms that lecturers remain highly committed to their roles, achieving significant outputs in teaching and research.

The findings of this study also reveal that lecturers in both DES demonstrate high levels of emotional intelligence. This suggests that lecturers across the two regions possess well-developed emotional competencies, including self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation, and relationship management. The high emotional intelligence levels indicate that these lecturers can effectively manage their own emotions while also recognizing and responding appropriately to the emotions of others. This

ability is especially valuable in academic environments, where emotional control and interpersonal sensitivity are essential for creating supportive learning atmospheres and sustaining productive relationships with students and colleagues.

A probable reason for the high levels of emotional intelligence observed in lecturers from both states could be the increasing recognition of the importance of emotional and social competencies in higher education. In recent years, many Nigerian universities have begun to emphasize EI as a key component of their teaching frameworks, recognizing its role in enhancing academic performance and improving classroom dynamics. Additionally, these lecturers may have benefited from various professional development initiatives, such as workshops and training programmes, which focus on enhancing emotional intelligence, a trend that is becoming more prevalent in Nigerian academic institutions.

These results are consistent with earlier research findings. Onoja, Ede, and Akande (2025) reported that university lecturers in Nigeria with higher emotional intelligence levels were more capable of managing stress and interacting effectively with students. Likewise, Seyi and Kazeem (2024) observed that educators who possess strong emotional intelligence exhibit better leadership and communication abilities, which foster more productive academic environments. The present study aligns with these findings, reinforcing the view that emotional intelligence positively influences lecturers' effectiveness and overall job performance.

Interestingly, while both groups of lecturers exhibited high levels of emotional intelligence, those from Edo State displayed slightly higher EI scores compared to their counterparts in Delta State. This suggests that Edo State lecturers may have more access to resources, training programmes, and institutional support aimed at developing emotional intelligence. It is possible that universities in Edo State place a stronger emphasis on professional development initiatives or that the socio-cultural and institutional environments in Edo are more conducive to fostering emotional intelligence.

A possible reason for this outcome may be the variation in the availability and implementation of emotional intelligence development programmes across the two states. Edo State universities might have more robust programmes or collaborations with international organizations that focus on emotional intelligence development for educators. Moreover, regional differences in educational policies and local community support may also contribute to the higher emotional intelligence scores observed in Edo State lecturers.

This finding is supported by past studies. Ogbeta-Ogwu (2024) found that Nigerian educators from universities with stronger institutional support and resources focused on emotional intelligence development exhibited higher EI scores. Their research indicated that lecturers from universities with better access to professional development programmes in EI were more likely to demonstrate high levels of emotional intelligence. Furthermore, a study by Adubale and Obioma (2025) revealed that lecturers in regions with better educational infrastructures, such as Edo State, consistently showed higher emotional intelligence. The research emphasized the importance of institutional and regional support in fostering the development of emotional intelligence among lecturers.

The results of this study indicate that lecturers in both DES possess high levels of emotional intelligence. However, lecturers in Edo State showed slightly higher EI levels, which may be attributed to stronger institutional support and greater access to professional development initiatives. These findings emphasize the need to promote emotional intelligence within academic environments, as it is vital for improving lecturers' performance, classroom interactions, and overall educational effectiveness.

Again, the study established a strong and positive correlation between emotional intelligence and job productivity among lecturers in both DES. This indicates that lecturers who are adept at managing emotions—both their own and others'—are more capable of performing well in their academic roles, which encompass teaching, research, and institutional responsibilities. From field interviews and discussions, lecturers frequently mentioned that self-awareness, emotional regulation, and interpersonal skills helped them manage workload pressures, student behaviour, and collaborative projects. Many shared experiences in which emotional intelligence enabled them to stay calm during crises, foster

supportive peer relationships, and maintain focus in high-stress situations—all of which contribute to enhanced productivity.

The statistical analysis further showed that emotional intelligence had a significantly stronger influence on job productivity among lecturers in Edo State compared to their counterparts in Delta State. The researcher attributes this difference to the more structured approach to emotional intelligence training observed in certain Edo-based institutions. Some of these universities included emotional intelligence modules in their performance evaluation frameworks or linked them to promotions and leadership appointments. Such systemic emphasis likely creates a stronger incentive for lecturers to develop and apply these skills consistently. This finding aligns with the work of Jaya et al. (2023), who observed that institutions that deliberately incorporate emotional intelligence training into their professional development programmes often experience greater job satisfaction, stronger teamwork, and enhanced academic performance.

From the researcher's perspective, these findings present a compelling case for institutions in Delta State to strengthen the emotional intelligence component of their staff development programmes. This may involve incorporating emotional intelligence as a key theme in leadership development, staff appraisal, and student engagement training. Doing so can contribute to improved workplace relationships, enhanced teaching quality, and greater resilience among lecturers.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that emotional intelligence significantly and positively influences the job productivity of university lecturers in DES, Nigeria. Lecturers from both states displayed high emotional intelligence levels, though those in Edo State recorded slightly higher scores than their counterparts in Delta State. The results further indicate that lecturers with stronger emotional intelligence tend to perform better in key areas such as lesson planning, student supervision, research activities, and involvement in institutional administration. Consequently, the study underscores the vital role of emotional intelligence in improving lecturers' productivity, with its impact appearing more pronounced among lecturers in Edo State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Universities should establish well-structured emotional intelligence development programmes for lecturers aimed at enhancing their self-awareness, emotional control, empathy, motivation, and interpersonal skills.
2. Institutional frameworks should be developed to support emotional intelligence development, including workshops, seminars, and peer learning groups focused on applying emotional intelligence in academic roles.
3. Emotional intelligence should be incorporated into performance evaluation and career advancement criteria to encourage lecturers to actively develop and apply EI in their professional lives.
4. Universities in Delta State should prioritize emotional intelligence programmes to address the regional disparity observed between Delta and Edo States and ensure equitable access to EI training resources.
5. Mentorship programmes should be established to allow senior lecturers to guide junior staff, fostering the development of emotional intelligence and enhancing job productivity through peer support.

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